

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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HEALTHCARE EXECUTIVES' HIRING PRACTICES OF ANESTHESIA
PROVIDERS IN FREESTANDING AMBULATORY SURGICAL CENTERS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

In California, Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNA) might practice as independent anesthesia providers at both inpatient and outpatient surgery centers. However, it is unclear whether CRNAs are being hired as independent anesthesia providers by the healthcare executives (HCEs) in the vast amount of free-standing Ambulatory Surgical Centers (ASCs) in California.

The American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) set research priorities focused on gaining knowledge about HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs. Guided by the need to explore decision-making factors when hiring an anesthesia provider, the author's project sought to provide additional knowledge that would support recommendations for CRNA advocacy efforts. This included conducting a survey of HCEs at freestanding ASCs in California, regarding their perceptions and hiring practices of CRNAs and anesthesiologists.

There were 665 surveys sent to HCEs through Qualtrics Survey Software, with 42 respondents. Out of the 27 HCEs who preferred to hire an anesthesiologist or a combination of an anesthesiologist and CRNAs, 15 (55.6%) were not aware of the current state and federal regulations regarding CRNA's independent standards of practice (SOP) in California. The other 12 (44.4%) were not sure or perceived that the surgeon had an increased risk of being held responsible for the anesthesia practices and could be held liable when utilizing CRNAs to deliver anesthesia services at ASCs. Ten (66.7%) of

the HCEs who reported that they did not currently hire CRNAs did not understand state regulations and laws regarding CRNAs SOP.

The results of this study were reported to the AANA, and recommendations were made that identified marketing strategies to mitigate misperceptions regarding CRNAs practices. One proposal to the AANA was to send representatives to the annual California Ambulatory Surgical Association (CASA) meeting to inform HCEs of CRNA SOP. A second recommendation highlighted the need for further research investigating patients' perceptions of the care they received from CRNAs. Survey results would be shared with the HCEs at their ASCs, thereby informing HCEs of the quality care provided by CRNAs.

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BACKGROUND

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project explored perceptions of healthcare executives (HCEs) and their practices when hiring anesthesia providers at freestanding ambulatory surgical centers (ASCs) in California. The American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) set research priorities focused on gaining knowledge about HCEs' perceptions of certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs), misperceptions HCEs may have of federal and state legislation relating to CRNAs, and factors considered when hiring anesthesia providers (J. Quraishi, personal communication, October 8, 2018; see Appendix A). Ms. Jihan Quraishi is the director of research and quality at the AANA and the author's AANA mentor. Ms. Quraishi specifically requested that ASCs in California be the focus of this DNP project to obtain data about hiring practices in these facilities. This project was designed to explore HCEs' perceptions at freestanding ASCs in California and report these findings to the AANA. This project has implications for CRNA practice, policy, and education, as the results may guide the development of marketing strategies regarding the benefits of hiring CRNAs in these settings.

Nationally, anesthesia is administered to patients by both anesthesiologists and CRNAs. The anesthesiologist is a physician provider, and a CRNA is a nurse provider. Both types of providers may work in inpatient hospital and outpatient surgical settings. National data from 2018 report that 75% of CRNAs worked primarily in the inpatient hospital setting and 16% worked in at least one ASC setting (AANA, 2018). In either type of setting, the level of physician supervision of CRNAs' practice varies from full medical direction to CRNAs independently delivering services. Until 2001, federal law

mandated that CRNAs be supervised by a physician when providing anesthesia services. In November of 2001, Congress passed the opt-out rule (Legislation 42 C.F.R), which allowed each state the option to remove this mandate. Currently, the scope of practice (SOP) laws governing CRNAs vary by state and drive practice and reimbursement (Negrusa, Hogan, Warner, Schroeder, & Pand, 2016).

In June of 2009, California Governor Schwarzenegger made California an opt-out state exempt from the federal mandate of physician supervision of CRNAs, allowing CRNAs to provide independent services. In the country, there are 422 hospitals and 794 ASCs (Baker, 2018; Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2017), and there are 1,988 CRNAs and 3,080 anesthesiologists practicing in one or both settings (AANA, 2018b). Within these settings, three types of service models are commonly used: CRNA only, anesthesiologist supervision of the CRNA, and anesthesiologist only. There are no empirical studies on factors that HCEs consider when deciding on a model of anesthesia service or for hiring anesthesia providers at ASCs.

The AANA (2019) reported that costs are tripled when anesthesiologists supervise CRNAs for the purposes of managing the perceived risk associated with hiring CRNAs. Traditionally, the base pay for an anesthesiologist is much higher than that of the CRNA. According to the Bureau of Labor Statistics (2017), the salary of an anesthesiologist is 2.5 times greater than the salary of a CRNA. However, the reimbursement rate for anesthesia services from medical insurance companies, including Medicare, is the same for both providers. Therefore, any work incentive cost to hire an anesthesiologist or a CRNA is paid by the facility from the insurance fees or private pay collected for reimbursable overhead expenses. Thus, it is difficult to argue that hiring an

anesthesiologist is more cost-effective when it costs more to hire an anesthesiologist. Therefore, the AANA requested that this DNP author focus her project on investigating perceptions and hiring practices and to identify gaps in knowledge HCEs may have, which may help to better understand if CRNAs are being utilized to the full scope of their practice allowances and as independent CRNAs at ASCs in California.

Supporting Framework

To provide boundaries and structure for clinical projects, Bonnel and Smith (2014) support the use of a framework, which increases projects' efficiency. Langley et al. (2009) support the use of the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) framework for a successful trial and learning process. These authors also state that using the PDSA framework is beneficial when trying to make improvements in an organization by applying new knowledge. Thus, the PDSA framework was used as a blueprint to encompass this project's development, implementation, and evaluation. The figure below illustrates the PDSA framework cycle.

Figure 1. PDSA cycle.

The PDSA cycle framework starts with a plan and ends with an action based on the learning of new knowledge from that plan. This framework has four steps that are on a feedback loop that continues based on meeting the project's aims. For this DNP project, during the Plan stage, factors that decision-makers may use when hiring anesthesia providers were examined. A literature review included possible additional factors that may also influence hiring decisions. The author developed a survey tool based on this new knowledge to investigate HCEs' perceptions. For the Do phase, a survey was distributed to explore their perspectives. The results of the survey were analyzed in the Study phase. During the Act phase, recommendations on marketing strategies were planned and distributed to the CRNA national organization based on the results of the survey.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the DNP project was to explore California HCEs' practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ASCs. The aims were threefold:

- Describe HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs and their practices when hiring both CRNAs and anesthesiologists, specifically in California ASCs;
- Identify gaps in knowledge, barriers to hiring, and other misconceptions regarding the CRNA role, scope of practice, and standards of practice;

Report the findings and make recommendations to the CRNA national organization to develop marketing strategies to mitigate misperceptions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The purpose of the DNP project was to explore HCEs' practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions regarding using anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ASCs in California. This section consists of a review of the literature, the methods used to retrieve the literature, and a description of the available research.

Methods of Retrieval

Initial search strategies for this literature review used One Search through the Pollack Library at California State University, Fullerton. Only literature written in English language was included for this project. The literature search was initially limited to articles published between 2005 and 2019. A second phase literature search included PubMed, EBSCO, CINAHL, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Collaboration. The initial search revealed limited relevant literature, so date limiters were not included to allow for all studies to be examined for relevancy. The topic of anesthesia is a specialized area of health care, so specific anesthesia-related resources were included. The author found one interesting anecdotal study regarding surgeons' perceptions and preference for hiring anesthesiologists, which is addressed in this literature review

Reference lists were examined for relevant literature. The search terms were safety of CRNAs verses anesthesiologists, physician anesthesia versus non-physician anesthesia provider safety, surgeon liability, viewpoints about CRNAs as anesthesia providers, viewpoint of executives about CRNAs or anesthesia providers, CRNA statistics, anesthesiologist statistics, ambulatory surgery, and CRNA utilization, ASCs in California, and utilization of CRNAs in opt-out and non-opt-out states. MeSH terms were

surgeons and (“viewpoints” or “attitudes” or “opinions”) and CRNA (or “nurse anesthetists” or “anesthesia”).

Safety: CRNA and Anesthesiologists

All members of the healthcare team must focus on patient safety. A Cochrane review evaluated whether one type of anesthesia provider was safer than another. Lewis, Nicholson, Smith, and Alderson (2014) concluded that, due to the vast difference in study methods, results, and low quality of evidence, no definitive statement could be made on whether there were differences in patient outcomes based on the type anesthesia provider. Since the publication of that review, other studies aimed to examine differences in patient outcomes when CRNAs or anesthesiologists provided services. Sun, Miller, Moshfegh, and Baker (2018) investigated differences in patient outcomes when anesthesiologists supervised CRNAs and when they supervised anesthesia assistants (AAs): AAs receive training that is different from that of CRNAs and is not licensed, providers. Sun et al. (2018) suggested that the care provided by either AA or CRNA, when supervised by an anesthesiologist, was not associated with significant differences in mortality, length of stay, or inpatient cost. This study, however, did not include the CRNA-only model.

Negrusa et al. (2016) aimed to test the odds of an anesthesia complication occurring during a procedure and the relation of the complication to the SOP and delivery model. In this study, anesthesia liability claims, and related complications were identified in a large commercial payer database, which included events that occurred in both inpatient and ASC settings in Virginia. Patient characteristics, patient comorbidities, procedure complexity, and local economic factors were statistically controlled, and the impact of state SOP and delivery model was analyzed. Delivery models were CRNA

only, anesthesiologist only, or mixed anesthesiologist and CRNA team. Results showed that complications were four times more likely in the inpatient setting (20 per 10,000) than the ASC setting (4 per 10,000.) This was noted to be due to procedures related to childbirth, which took place only in inpatient surgical settings. In both settings, the odds of a complication differed significantly according to patient characteristics, comorbidities, and procedures (Negrusa et al., 2016.). Complication odds were not found to differ by the SOP or anesthesia delivery model.

Liability

Early literature suggested surgeons thought there was a higher risk if an independent CRNA delivered anesthesia care than if an anesthesiologist were present either in the supervising role or as the sole provider (Blumenreich, 1991). Other anecdotal evidence suggested liability remains a concern. Sikes (2016), the author of an internet blog, is the chief of operations of a hospital group of physicians and anesthesia providers. He described the concern of surgeon liability when working with CRNAs. Sikes indicated liability is a common question discussed among all healthcare staff, especially surgeons. This concept is known as the captain of the ship argument. Silbermann (2016) suggested additional reasons that surgeons choose anesthesiologists only as (a) the thought that state or federal legislation required a CRNA be supervised and directed by an anesthesiologist; (b) perceptions that better patient outcomes were associated with an anesthesiologist providing or supervising care; and (c) thoughts that the surgeon's professional and financial liability risk was lower when working with an anesthesiologist.

The concern of liability is not new and evident when Tammelleo (1994) sought to understand whether the captain of the ship perception was based on actual liability case rulings. This author examined the case of *Harris v. Miller*, where an orthopedic surgeon was involved in a malpractice and wrongful death case in which he was the mandated supervising physician of the CRNA named in the surgical case. The blood loss from the surgical case contributed to anesthesia complications of lower blood pressures. Although the surgeon was named as a defendant in the case by the prosecution, he claimed that, even though the CRNA made him aware complications were presenting, his supervisory role did not constitute control of anesthesia care or the CRNA's practice choices. Because the surgeon was made aware of the complication and was the only physician in the room, the prosecution claimed the surgeon should assume full responsibility for the patient outcome. The judge ruled that the CRNA was fully responsible, and the surgeon was not held liable (Tammelleo, 1994).

Other court rulings have shown that a surgeon's liability does not vary based on anesthesia provider type but does vary based on the involvement of the surgeon in the anesthesia care. Examples of these court cases provide evidence that surgeons are not held liable when working with a CRNA any differently than when they work with anesthesiologists (Blumenreich, 1991, 1997, 1998). For additional court cases and rulings, please see Appendix B. The DNP author does acknowledge that the misconception of higher liability when using a CRNA may still be a factor in HCEs' hiring practices. Therefore, this belief was investigated as part of her project.

Perceptions of Healthcare Executives

Limited empirical evidence compares the viewpoints of HCEs in terms of patient care when delivered by CRNAs and anesthesiologists. One small qualitative study of 24 operating room personnel examined their comfort level when working with a CRNA (Hensel, Cooper, & Craney, 2016). Participants completed a -4 to +4 rank-ordering of agreement with 34 attitude statements of beliefs about nurse anesthetists. Three viewpoints emerged that explained 66% of the variance: 27% variance favoring unrestricted practice of CRNA, 16% variance favoring supervision of CRNA, and 13% variance favored anesthesiologist only. The authors did explain that one participant was a surgeon, and another was an anesthesiologist. Hensel et al. (2016) did not indicate how these two participants responded, but they did state that one physician favored the unrestrictive practice of CRNAs, and the other favored supervision of CRNAs by anesthesiologists. The other participants were 17 registered nurses and five operating room technicians. No other studies investigating perceptions on care provided by CRNAs or anesthesiologists were found that included HCEs as part of the sample. Hensel et al. did recommend further research to determine how workplace attitudes can be changed to support the autonomous practice by CRNAs. To this end, the author's DNP project sought to explore perceptions of HCEs about CRNAs to recommend strategies that would promote the hiring of CRNAs in ASCs.

Summary

No empirical evidence was found regarding the perceptions of HCEs related to decision making when hiring CRNAs and anesthesiologists in ASCs. The evidence showed that anesthesia care delivered by independent CRNAs is safe and consistent with

the care provided by anesthesiologists. Anecdotal reports showed that, currently, surgeons continue to be concerned about the perceived greater liability when working with a CRNA (Sikes, 2016). Additional research is needed to identify factors that HCEs use when making hiring decisions. Therefore, guided by the need to explore decision-making factors, the author's project sought to provide additional knowledge that would support recommendations for CRNA advocacy efforts.

METHODS

The purpose of the DNP project was to explore HCEs' practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ASCs in California. Due to the limited empirical data regarding HCEs' hiring practices and perceptions, the author chose an exploratory design. Grove, Gray, and Burns (2015) support the use of this design when research on the topic is limited or lacking. In this section, the procedural plan used to obtain HCEs' perceptions and hiring practices is explained as well as how the sample was obtained, and how the survey tool (Appendix C) was developed.

Ethical Considerations

The project's proposal was submitted to the California State University, Long Beach, Institutional Review Board, and was granted approval as an exempt project (Appendix D). The survey used in this project was designed, so that implied consent was achieved when a participant chose to complete the anonymous survey. There were no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this project, with the exception of disclosure of the respondent's opinion regarding the hiring of anesthesia providers. Participation in the project was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time by exiting the survey.

Sample

The total number of HCEs employed in ASCs in California was not available in any data bank known to the author. To obtain a convenience sample of self-identified HCEs, three different lists of HCEs' email addresses were obtained and used to contact subjects. The first attempts involved phone calls to freestanding ASCs in California

where the HCEs were employed. A web page (Ambulatory Surgery Center Association, n.d.) listed the names and contact phone numbers of 794 ASCs in California. To obtain access to the HCEs' email addresses, the author placed a call to each ASC listed on the webpage. Additional assistance was obtained from a research assistant who followed directions specific to this project's acceptance. A scripted message was read by both the author and research assistant asking for the HCE's email address (Appendix E). Over six weeks, attempts were made to contact employees who were willing to provide their HCE's email address. Calls were made to the 794 ASCs; however, 123 calls were not answered or went to a discontinued number. A final number of 641 calls were made, including when only a scripted message could be left. Out of this call list, 148 HCEs' email addresses were obtained and added to the survey distribution list. From those emails, 39 bounced, 2 were duplicates, and two failed to be sent. From this process, 105 HCEs received the survey via email. A second list was purchased by the DNP author from the company Complete Medical List for approximately \$1,000. This list included the names and contact information for 250 HCEs at various ASCs across California. From this list, 21 emails bounced, and one failed to be sent. The total number of HCEs contacted from this list was 228. Lastly, additional names and email addresses were obtained from a list of attendees at a California Ambulatory Surgical Center Association meeting. This list was received from a senior member of the association and included 350 HCEs. From that list, 15 emails bounced, two were duplicates, and one failed to be sent.

The number of HCEs who received the survey was 665. The HCEs at the freestanding ASCs recruited for this project were those involved in the hiring of anesthesia service providers: the chief executive officer, chief financial officer, chief

marketing officer, the medical director of surgical services, or chief nursing officer. Surgeons who provided surgical services at the ASC were also identified as HCEs because they often are financially invested in the ASCs (Baker, 2018). However, only surgeons who were invested in the ASC were recruited to complete the survey. Only HCEs from freestanding ASCs were recruited for this project. It was anticipated that the response rate would be 5% to 10%, consistent with the expected completion of an external survey.

Setting

The project's setting was freestanding ASCs in California. According to the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, an ASC is defined as a distinct entity that operates exclusively for the purpose of furnishing outpatient surgical services to patients (Ambulatory Surgical Center, 1982). Freestanding ASCs are not affiliated with an inpatient hospital.

Instrument

Qualtrics™ is an internet platform used to collect and analyze data through surveys. This platform was used to distribute a survey link to the HCEs' email addresses. The survey (Appendix C) consisted of 10 questions to explore HCEs' hiring practices and their perceptions regarding CRNAs. Only ten questions were selected based on personal discussions with local California HCEs as to the maximum number of questions they would be willing to answer in a survey. The questions' content was based on the HCEs' perceptions that could influence hiring practices, a request for specific information from the AANA, and current state and federal regulations regarding CRNAs. The question items were developed by the author and examined by this project's team leader, an

independent research expert, an independent marketing professional, and one CRNA professional who was also a team member of this DNP project. Two questions on demographics were included, along with one open-ended question. The survey items included various types of questions that called for selection among multiple choices, rating responses using a 5-point Likert scale, and “yes” or “no” responses. A comment section was also provided. Participants were able to skip questions and move backward and forward throughout the survey. Appendix C displays the survey questions as they appeared on the website.

The face validity of the survey was evaluated by an expert panel consisting of a California State University, Long Beach faculty member with expertise in research design, one member from the AANA Department of Research, and a marketing specialist who is a professional regional recruiter for physicians and CRNAs. The author asked the expert panel to evaluate the survey questions and suggest changes. The consensus among the three expert panel members was needed for the question item and its response selections to remain part of the questionnaire. The consensus was reached within two months. At the end of the survey, a link to the AANA website was provided for participants who desired more information about CRNAs’ SOP and federal and state regulations regarding the practice of CRNAs.

Data Collection/ Management

An electronic link to the survey was sent directly to HCEs through Qualtrics™. Distribution of the survey was done weekly to the email addresses obtained from phone calls and the generated distribution lists. Survey recruitment took place from August 1, 2019, through October 31, 2019. To improve response rates, three follow-up reminders

were emailed to each HCE at 1, 2, and 4 weeks after the first email was sent. After the last reminders were sent, the survey was closed on November 1, 2019. Survey data from the Qualtrics™ file were downloaded to an Excel file, and data were analyzed.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic variables. Results were examined to determine whether there were any differences between HCEs who did not hire CRNAs as independent providers and those who did, especially regarding knowledge of California state law and regulations for the provisions of anesthesia services, perceived risk of liability, and perceived safety when care is delivered by an anesthesiologist versus a CRNA.

RESULTS

The purpose of the DNP project was to explore HCEs' practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ASCs in California. This section presents the results of the data analysis.

The author distributed 778 emails to HCEs through Qualtrics™ and, with duplicate and bounced emails excluded, 665 were delivered based on the Qualtrics data submission report. Forty-four recipients opened the survey for a response rate of 6.6%. Of that forty-four, two subjects responded that they did not agree to the consent terms and did not continue the survey for a final sample size of 42. In reviewing the survey responses, the DNP project author noted that some respondents chose not to answer specific questions; therefore, actual response numbers for each survey question did vary and are noted throughout the results section.

When asked the number of ASCs in which the HCE was responsible for hiring anesthesia providers, 32 respondents answered this question. Most, 22 of the 32 respondents (68.8%), stated one center, eight (25%) answered two to five centers, and two (6.25%) reported more than five centers. Thirty-two HCEs reported on the various type of surgical services provided at their ASC. General surgery was the most frequent type of surgical services provided in their ASCs as reported by 21 respondents (65.6%), followed by 19 (59.4%) respondents noting Orthopedics services, 18 (56.3%) Gastrointestinal (GI) services, 18 (56.3%) Plastic Surgery services, 17 (53.1%) Podiatry services, 16 (50%) Ophthalmology, 15 (46.9%) Urology services, 14 (43.8%) reported Gynecology, and seven (21.9 %) reported "other "services, but not specified. Thirty-two participants answered the question on the preference of the type of anesthesia provider to

hire. Of these responses, three (9.4%) preferred CRNAs only, 17 (53.1%) preferred anesthesiologist, 11 (34.4%) indicated a combination of both, and one (3.1%) indicated no preference. When asked if they perceived that a surgeon would be more at risk and held accountable for a malpractice claim when using a CRNA, 12 of the 31 (38.7%) respondents perceive this to be true or were not sure.

Regarding the understanding of state law and regulation for the provision of anesthesia services in California ASCs, 15 of the 31 (48.4%) respondents to this question were not knowledgeable about California laws relating to CRNAs' SOP (i.e., CRNAs can be independent practitioners). When asked if they perceived a difference in adhering to patient safety standards and quality of patient care between anesthesiologists and CRNAs, 27 of the 31 (87.1%) survey participants agreed there was no difference.

Factors that are important to HCEs when hiring anesthesia providers were rated individually on a scale of least important to most important. Therefore, participants could choose several factors that they found "most important." The most frequent answers chosen as the most important factors were safety by 27 of the 31 respondents (87.1%), and 23 chose collaboration (74.2%). Factors that were reported as less important shown by choosing a one, two, or three responses were surgeon preference by 11 (35.5%) and academic background by 15 HCEs (48.4%). Table 1 identifies factors considered in hiring decisions and their perceived importance by the HCEs sample ($N=31$) when hiring an anesthesia provider. Figure 2 shows a visual representation of the combined results comparing the means of each factor that contributed to the hiring factors of CRNAs.

Table 1

Factors Contributing to HCEs Hiring Practices of Anesthesia Providers (N=31)

Factor (%)	Least Important	2	3	4	Most Important
Cost- The cost to employ and reimbursement rates	6.45%	9.68%	12.90%	32.2%	38.71%
Availability- Number and type of providers available to be hired	3.23%	9.68%	16.13%	35.4%	35.48%
Collaboration- Establishes a supportive relationship with the surgical team	3.23%	6.45%	3.23%	16.1%	70.9%
Safety- Delivery of anesthesia based on best practice standards	6.45%	0.00%	3.23%	3.23%	87.1%
Surgeons preference	9.68%	16.13%	6.45%	25.8%	41.94%
Academic Background- Educational levels of MD versus CRNAs	3.23%	6.45%	38.71%	32.2%	19.35%

Figure 2. Hiring Factors Comparing Means

Thirty-two HCEs responded to the question regarding clinical privileges granted to CRNAs at their ASC. Out of the 32 HCEs who responded to this question, 15 (46.9%) reported they did not currently hire nurse anesthetists, and 17 indicated the type(s) of clinical CRNA privilege(s) at their ASC. The rank order of clinical privileges of CRNAs at the ASCs were Monitored Anesthesia Care (MAC) reported by 13 HCEs (76.5%), followed by nine (52.9%) reporting their CRNAs engaging in the practice of general anesthesia, five (29.4%) administering local anesthesia, four (23.5%) administering epidural/spinal anesthesia, and three (17.6%) permitted CRNAs to provide nerve blocks. The job title of the HCEs were self-reported ($N=33$): eight (24.2 %) were chief executive officers, one (3.0%) was a chief financial officer, one (3.0%) was a medical director, nine (27.3%) were chief nursing officers, one (3.0%) was a surgeon, and 13 (39.4%) indicated an “other” designation.

Out of the 27 HCEs who preferred to hire anesthesiologists or a combination of anesthesiologists and CRNAs only, 15 (55.6%) were not aware of the current state and federal regulations regarding CRNA SOP allowances in California. Out of the 32 HCEs who responded, 15 (46.9%) reported they did not currently hire nurse anesthetists. Ten (66.7%) of the HCEs’ who reported that they do not currently hire CRNAs did not understand state regulations and laws regarding these regulations. Out of the 31 respondents who reported their preference of anesthesia providers, 27 (87.1%) HCEs preferred an anesthesiologist to be present either with a CRNA or alone. Of these 27 HCEs, 12 (44.4%) were not sure or perceived that the surgeon had an increased risk of being held responsible for the anesthesia practices and could be held liable when utilizing CRNAs to deliver anesthesia services at ASCs.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the DNP project was to explore HCEs practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ASCs in California. The aims were to identify gaps in knowledge, barriers to hiring, and other misconceptions about the CRNA role, SOP, and standards of practice. Further, the aim was to report the findings and make recommendations to the CRNA national organization to develop marketing strategies to mitigate misperceptions.

The results of this study clearly showed that HCEs prefer hiring anesthesiologists at ASCs in California; however, the reasons why were less clear. The safety of the patient is at the center of all health care, including anesthesia services. In this DNP project, most N=28 (90.3%) HCEs reported they perceived the same level of adherence to patient safety standards and quality of patient care among both anesthesiologists and CRNAs. Additionally, the most important factor when deciding on an anesthesia provider by most respondents was patient safety. Anesthesia continues to be delivered safely and effectively by both anesthesiologists and CRNAs. Lewis, Nicholson, Smith, and Alderson (2014) reported they could not determine whether there was any difference in patient safety based on the type of anesthesia provider alone. Negrusa et al. (2016) also found that the odds of an anesthesia complication were not found to differ by the SOP or anesthesia delivery model. This project's findings support Silbermann's (2016) assertion that an additional reason a surgeon chose to partner with anesthesiologists only is their perception that better patient outcomes were associated with an anesthesiologist providing or supervising care. It stands to reason that if safety is the top priority when hiring an anesthesia provider and safe anesthesia delivery has been shown to not differ

between anesthesiologists and CRNAs, then other factors are contributing to choosing an anesthesiologist by HCEs at ASCs in California.

Gaps in knowledge regarding the extent of the scope of practice of CRNAs, as well as state and federal regulations regarding the hiring of independent CRNAs were apparent based on the project findings. This could, in fact, be a prevailing issue of why HCEs are not hiring CRNAs. Although there is no empirical evidence, it is reasonable to assume HCEs would not hire an independent CRNA if they believed it was illegal to do so. This does support Silbermann's (2016) contention that surgeons may choose anesthesiologists only because they believe state or federal legislation requires a CRNA to be supervised and directed by an anesthesiologist.

Surgeon liability is both a historical and current concern of HCEs. As discussed in the Review of Literature section, court rulings in malpractice cases have continuously documented that there is no increase in liability for surgeons when working with an independent CRNA (Blumenreich, 1998; Sikes, 2016). However, the results of this DNP project showed that some HCEs still perceived this to be true. If HCEs' fear unnecessary liability claims, their uneasiness in hiring CRNAs is understandable; however, the many case reports have shown that this fear is unsubstantiated by court rulings (Appendix B).

When considering the other factors that contribute to the hiring of anesthesia providers at ASCs, the educational background was rated as less critical. This is interesting in that the different academic and clinical backgrounds of the anesthesia provider (MD vs. RN) is the obvious difference between a physician anesthesiologist and a CRNA.

Limitations

Survey design studies have inherent limitations that have the potential to impact the validity of the findings. Sample characteristic limitations and small respondent sample size may also limit the generalizability of study results. Self-reporting methodology raises the possibility of participant bias related to demand characteristics and social desirability response set (Morgado, Fabiane, Meireles, Juliana, Neves, et al., 2017). Regional bias could have occurred if the participants had experience with only one type of anesthesia provider and based all answers on personal experiences. For example, an HCE may have based all answers on working with an anesthesia group that hired only anesthesiologists and was, therefore, unable to answer questions regarding CRNAs. Missing data may also bias parameter estimations, which are associated with an increased risk of reaching incorrect conclusions.

An explicit limitation to this project was the low response rate of the HCEs survey. Nonetheless, to obtain the necessary data needed for this project, exploratory design was required to collect specific information to add to the body of knowledge about the hiring practices of CRNAs. Allowing the survey to stay open longer to reach the HCEs may have increased sample size. One wonders if the low response rate was in part due to the design of the survey, and/or whether HCEs knew the intent was about exploring issues related to why CRNAs are not being hired in increasing numbers at ASCs. It could be assumed then, that HCEs who work closely with only anesthesiologist or have no experience with CRNAs in their employment setting would not consider participating in the survey because of a very close relationship and network in working with doctors with whom they felt obliged to continue their partnership. However, for this

project, factors that the HCEs may likely consider when hiring anesthesia providers were examined, and the survey findings provided useful information related to the aims of this project.

The survey was designed based on available empirical research. The respondents of the survey did not choose to include any narrative comments that might have identified additional factors that HCEs may consider in their decisions to hire CRNAs. If, in fact, there are additional factors that HCEs may use when hiring anesthesia providers that were not identified during the review of the literature and included in the survey, the results of this study may not be a clear indication of HCEs perspectives.

Recommendations/ Implications

The AANA established research priorities focused on gaining knowledge about HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs, identifying HCEs' misperceptions of federal and state legislation relating to CRNAs, and determining factors HCEs consider when hiring anesthesia providers (J. Quraishi, personal communication, October 8, 2018; see Appendix A). After reviewing project results and consulting with the project team, this author sent an executive summary to the AANA with recommendations for CRNA advocacy efforts (Appendix F).

Misconceptions about legal mandates, as opposed to actual laws and regulations, should not guide the practice of hiring CRNAs in ASCs as independent anesthesia providers. HCEs need to become more familiar with the SOP of CRNAs and the role of CRNAs in health care. Marketing strategies directed at correcting misconceptions should be the focus of AANA's efforts to decrease HCEs' gap in knowledge.

This author recommended two specific strategies to the AANA based on the results of this exploratory project. The first strategy involves informing HCEs of best evidence-based practices related to the hiring of CRNAs at ASCs. This recommendation would require AANA representation and attendance at a CASA annual meeting, which could include a poster presentation, having an exhibit booth, as well as one to one effort to dialogue with the HCEs about concerns they may have regarding CRNAs. This presence would establish professional relationships between CRNAs and HCEs in California to help increase the hiring of CRNAs for ASCs. Although there is a financial cost to this meeting, the benefits of this advocacy strategy would be significant both for CRNA's in California and the nation. California has the largest number of ASCs in the nation, representing a large percentage of the nation's HCEs within ASCs (Ambulatory Surgery Center Association, n.d.). The booth would be staffed with AANA members knowledgeable about legal and current CRNA SOP regulations. A professional poster would be featured in the booth to highlight current state and federal regulations regarding CRNA SOP, best evidence-based practice research related to CRNAs practices, and examples of court rulings to decrease the fear of legal repercussions when hiring an independent CRNA.

The CRNA anesthesia group, Sweet Dreams Anesthesia™, reserved an Elite level booth at the September 2020 CASA meeting. If time allows, contacting this group and sharing the results and recommendations of this project could provide a speedy way for the AANA to inform the HCEs of the best evidence-based practices.

A second recommendation highlights the need for further research investigating patients' perceptions of the care they received from CRNAs. The survey could be part of

a post-operative patient questionnaire designed to understand the patients' experiences while receiving care at the ASC. Survey results would be shared with the HCEs at their ASCs, thereby informing HCEs about the quality of care provided by CRNAs. Also, information regarding CRNA practice would be included on the back of the patient survey. It would be geared toward educating the general public and highlighting the specific needs of the anesthesia patient. This survey could be distributed to HCEs at all ASCs in California. The AANA website could also provide a digital version, where CRNAs could print out and distribute the survey to their patients.

Here you would describe the results in terms of the supporting framework and literature reviewed. This section could also be titled Conclusions or Recommendations for Practice or Implications for Practice. In the case of a doctoral project with a product such as a procedure or protocol, this section could be titled Potential Implementation Plan, and would outline steps to take in implementing the product.

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APPENDIX A

PROJECT SUGGESTION FROM AANA

Project Suggestions - Message (HTML)
File Message Help Tell me what you want to do

Jihan Quraishi

Project Suggestions

10/8/2018

county_CA_map.pdf
196 KB

Dear Amy,

It was a pleasure speaking with you. It sounds like you have a very exciting project on your hands.

As I mentioned during our call, California has been a somewhat perplexing state for the AANA. While California is an opt-out state, it is also an anesthesiologist dominant state (see state map attached). While California has a significant number of university academic centers and providers working in Kaiser, we have very limited information about how anesthesia is delivered in outpatient facilities. In many instances, it unclear how anesthesia delivery models are chosen outside of these large facilities and why.

Both the AANA and AANA Foundation has developed a set of [research priorities](#) at the national level. The first major question aims at understanding healthcare executive perceptions...see below.

- What are healthcare executives (CEOs, CFOs, CMOs, and CNOs) perceptions of CRNA anesthesia services and how do they value the cost of care provided by CRNAs in their institutional settings? (variations by type of hospital, location by state, location by rural versus city)

While this question focuses on executive perceptions of anesthesia services for inpatient facilities by geographic location, a subset of questions addressing the surgeon/proceduralist perception of anesthesia services in an ambulatory surgery center or outpatient facility is just as important. These research questions aim qualitatively identifying potential gaps, barriers, and misconceptions other key decision makers may have with regards to state and federal regulations and reimbursement.

The question above was developed and prioritized by the AANA Health Services Research Ad Hoc Committee comprising of 8 AANA member researchers representing each affiliate (AANA, AANA Foundation, COA, and NBCRNA). Please visit the AANA Foundation [Health Policy Research](#) initiative page to learn more about the research and prioritization process.

Sincerely,

Jihan Quraishi, MS, RN, AE-C, CCRC
Director of Research and Quality

APPENDIX B

LEGAL CASE RESULTS

<i>Summary of Legal Cases and Liability</i>			
Citation & Purpose	Location	Case	Findings
Surgeon not liable for CRNA: No “borrowed servant.” Case in point: Harris V. Miller 438 S. E. 2d 731 NC (Tammelleo, 1994).	Supreme Court of North Carolina and Oklahoma Courts.	Harris vs. Miller	Orthopedic surgeon and CRNA. The patient claimed vicarious liability against the surgeon. Courts ruled that CRNA held sole liability.
Legal briefs: Standard of care (Blumenreich, 1997). Purpose: Cases examined how courts look at each type of provider, CRNA, and Anesthesiologists.	Supreme Court of Iowa Louisiana Tennessee Texas	Carolan v. Hill Young v. Department of Health & Human Resources Goodman v. Phythyon Webb v. Jorns	CRNAs recognized by the courts as expert witnesses.
Legal briefs: Anesthesia and the surgeon’s comfort (Blumenreich, 1991).	North County Appellate Court Nebraska, 1991 New Jersey, 1991	Harris v. Miller Swierczek v. Lynch Lanzet v. Greenberg	Courts determined that the surgeon did not have the right to control anesthesia administration. The anesthesiologist was not an employee of the surgeon. The court ruled to bring in a surgeon to negligence even though he was not in the room when a positioning a patient who had nerve damage post-op. Surgeon held solely liable.

Note: CRNA = Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists, MD = Medical Doctor
Anesthesiologists = Medical Doctors of Anesthesia.

APPENDIX C

HEALTHCARE EXECUTIVE SURVEY

Consent.

Survey Information

My name is Amy Marks and I am a Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (CRNA) enrolled in the Southern California CSU Doctor of Nursing Practice program. I am interested in healthcare executive perceptions that influence their hiring decisions related to anesthesia providers. I am using a web-based online survey to obtain the information, which should take approximately 3 minutes to complete. Your participation in this project is voluntary. You may refuse or discontinue your participation at any time. Should you agree to participate, you are free to decline to answer any questions you do not wish to answer while completing the survey. You will receive no direct benefits from participating in this project. However, if you are willing to provide a follow-up email, you will be contacted with the final write-up of the project. There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this project. Responses will be stored on a password protect laptop. The survey was developed using Qualtrics™, an online survey software program in which data can be stored.

All data will be de-identified, and should the project be published, no identifying information will be included. All responses to the survey will remain confidential. I have set this Qualtrics™ survey to anonymize responses with no personal information or contact association recorded. This includes deletion of the IPA function for retrieval. Please select your choice below. You may print a copy of this consent form for your records. Clicking on the "Agree" button indicates that you have read the above information, are voluntarily agreeing to participate in the project, and are 18 years of age or older. Thank you for taking the time to read this letter. You may contact the Office of Research and Sponsored Programs at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu, or call [\(562\) 985-8147](tel:5629858147), if you have questions about your rights as a research participant.

agree

disagree

Q1. How many ambulatory surgical centers are you responsible for the decision making of hiring anesthesia providers?

- 1
- 2-5
- More than 5

Q2. PLEASE ANSWER THE FOLLOWING QUESTIONS BASED ON YOUR PRIMARY/ LARGEST AMBULATORY SURGERY CENTER (ASC)

Please indicate the type of surgical services provided at your ASC. (Check all that apply)

- General Surgery
- Orthopedics
- GYN
- Urology
- GI
- Podiatry
- Ophthalmology
- Plastics
- Other

Q3. Which of the following providers do you prefer to hire to deliver anesthesia services in ASCs?

- Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist
- Anesthesiologist
- Combination of Both
- No Preference

Q4. Do you perceive that a surgeon will be more at risk and held accountable for a malpractice claim when working with an independent CRNA?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

Q5. Based on your understanding of California state law and regulations for the provision of anesthesia services, are CRNAs allowed to provide anesthesia without physician supervision?

- Yes
 No
 Not Sure

Q6. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement. There is no difference in adhering to patient safety standards and the quality of patient care between anesthesiologists and CRNAs.

- Strongly agree
 Agree
 Somewhat agree
 Neither agree nor disagree
 Somewhat disagree
 Disagree
 Strongly disagree

Q7. On a scale from 1-5 (1 being the least and five being the most), how important are the following factors in the decision to hire an anesthesia provider

	1	2	3	4	5
Cost- The cost to employ and reimbursement rates	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
Availability- Number and type of providers available to be hired	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
Collaboration- Establishes a supportive relationship with the surgical team	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
Safety- Delivery of anesthesia based on best practice standards	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5

	1	2	3	4	5
Surgeons preference	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
Academic Background- Educational levels of MD versus CRNAs	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5

Q8. Clinical privileges of CRNAs in your facility includes which of the following type(s) of anesthesia delivery? (Check all that apply)?

- General
- Epidural/ Spinal
- Local
- Monitored Anesthesia Care
- Nerve Blocks
- Not sure
- We don't currently hire nurse anesthetists

Q9. Indicate your Job Title (Check all that apply)

- Chief Executive Officer
- Chief Financial Officer
- Chief Marketing Officer
- Medical Director
- Chief Nursing Office
- Surgeon – Financial Partnership
- Other

Q10. Please provide any additional comments regarding factors that affect your decision to hire anesthesia providers.

I

In addition, for more information on CRNAs scope of practice and federal and state regulations when hiring a CRNA, please visit www.aana.com.

APPENDIX D

IRB APPROVAL

**CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH
OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE: August 5, 2019

TO: Amy Marks, BSN, MSN

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1459815-2] Healthcare Executives Hiring Practices of Anesthesia Providers for Freestanding Ambulatory Surgical Centers

REFERENCE #: 20-023

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

REVIEW TYPE: Administrative Review

ACTION: APPROVED

APPROVAL DATE: August 5, 2019

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Your application is approved by Administrative Review according to the U.S. Department of Health & Human Services regulation at 45 CFR 46.104(d)(2)(4).

Approval is effective beginning August 5, 2019 and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy:

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form and recruitment material as follows: "**Approved August 5, 2019 by the CSULB IRB.**"
2. If you need to make changes/revisions to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol form in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to your approved project in IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of your Amendment from the CSULB IRB.
3. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORSP Compliance within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.
5. Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to call the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs at (562) 985-8147. We wish you the best of success in your research. This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State

University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records. 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840 Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

APPENDIX E
PHONE SCRIPT

Script: DNP student (or helper) calls ASCs in California from a list

Hello,/Good morning/afternoon/evening!

My name is Amy Marks (or another helper), and I am (helping) a DNP student from California State University School of Nursing Consortium.

I would like to contact Healthcare Executives responsible for hiring anesthesia providers at your facility to ask them if they are willing to participate in a survey that is a part of my DNP project. For this study, A Healthcare Executive can be your facility chief executive officers (CEO), chief financial officer (CFO), chief marketing officers (CMO), medical directors of surgical services, or chief nursing officers (CNO) and surgeons who are invested in the center.

Is there an email address where I may attempt to contact them?

If I need to leave a message, I will provide them with my personal cell phone number and school email. (949-910-8000, amymarks.csu.fullerton.edu)

Thank you for talking with me today.

APPENDIX F

EMAIL TO AANA

Ms. Quraishi, My DNP project is completed, and I wanted to share my findings with you. It has been a long and rewarding project, and I hope that the AANA and CRNAs will benefit from my hard work. I appreciate all that you have personally contributed to my project and its success. I look forward to your comments and suggestions regarding disseminating the results of this DNP project.

The AANA and AANA Foundation set research priorities focused on understanding healthcare executive perceptions of CRNAs. The purpose of the DNP project was to explore California healthcare executives' (HCE) practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus CRNAs in ambulatory surgery centers (ASCs). The aims were threefold: Describe HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs and their practices when hiring both CRNAs and anesthesiologists, specifically in California ASCs; Identify gaps in knowledge, barriers to hiring, and other misconceptions regarding the CRNA role, scope of practice, and standards of practice; Report the findings and make recommendations to the CRNA national organization to develop marketing strategies to mitigate misperceptions.

Attached to this email is my executive summary of my DNP project, recommendations based on the results, and a plan for implementation of the recommendations. Please feel free to contact me for further information or a copy of my completed project paper.

With Joy,
Amy Marks, CRNA

HEALTHCARE EXECUTIVES' HIRING PRACTICES OF ANESTHESIA PROVIDERS IN FREESTANDING AMBULATORY SURGICAL

Executive Summary

Amy Marks, CRNA

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to explore healthcare executives' (HCE) practices when hiring anesthesia providers and their perceptions about the utilization of anesthesiologists versus Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNA). The aims were threefold; to describe HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs and their practices when hiring both CRNAs and anesthesiologists, specifically in California Ambulatory Surgical Centers (ASC); to identify gaps in knowledge, barriers to hiring, and other misconceptions regarding the CRNA role, scope of practice, and standards of practice; and report the findings and make recommendations to the CRNA national organization to develop marketing strategies to mitigate misperceptions.

Background

In California, CRNAs may legally practice as independent anesthesia providers in both inpatient and outpatient surgery centers. However, it is unclear if CRNAs are being hired as independent anesthesia providers by the HCEs for the surgical procedures being performed at the vast number of freestanding ASCs in California. The American Association of Nurse Anesthetists (AANA) set research priorities focused on gaining knowledge about HCEs' perceptions of CRNAs. Guided by the need to explore decision-making factors when hiring an anesthesia provider, the author's project sought to provide additional knowledge that would support recommendations for CRNA advocacy efforts.

Methodology

Qualtrics™ is an internet platform that was used to collect and analyze data through surveys. This platform was used to distribute a survey link to the HCEs' email addresses. This survey consisted of 10 questions to explore HCEs' hiring practices and their perceptions regarding CRNAs. To obtain a convenience sample of self-identified HCEs, three different lists of HCEs' email addresses were obtained and used to contact subjects. The number of HCEs who received the survey was 665. The HCEs at the freestanding ASCs recruited for this project were those involved in the hiring of anesthesia service providers: the chief executive officer, chief financial officer, chief marketing officer, the medical director of surgical services, or chief nursing officer. Only HCEs from freestanding ASCs were recruited for this project.

Results

There were 42 respondents. Data collected and analyzed showed that 27 HCEs of the X respondents preferred to hire anesthesiologist or a combination of anesthesiologist and CRNAs only, 15 (55.6%) were not aware of current state and federal regulations regarding CRNA scope of practice allowances in California, 12 (44.4%) were not sure or perceived that the surgeon had an increased risk of being held responsible for the anesthesia practices and could be held liable when utilizing CRNAs to deliver anesthesia services at ASCs, and ten (66.7%) of the HCEs reported that they do not currently hire

CRNAs. Additional factors that HCEs use when considering hiring anesthesia providers were evaluated and are reported in Table 1 and Figure 1 below.

Table 1

Factors Contributing to HCEs Hiring Practices of Anesthesia Providers (N=31)

Factor (%)	Least Important	2	3	4	Most Important
Cost- The cost to employ and reimbursement rates	6.45%	9.68%	12.90%	32.2%	38.71%
Availability- Number and type of providers available to be hired	3.23%	9.68%	16.13%	35.4%	35.48%
Collaboration- Establishes a supportive relationship with the surgical team	3.23%	6.45%	3.23%	16.1%	70.9%
Safety- Delivery of anesthesia based on best practice standards	6.45%	0.00%	3.23%	3.23%	87.1%
Surgeons preference	9.68%	16.13%	6.45%	25.8%	41.94%
Academic Background- Educational levels of MD versus CRNAs	3.23%	6.45%	38.71%	32.2%	19.35%

Figure 1. Hiring Factors Comparing Means

Recommendations

Misconceptions about legal mandates as oppose to actual laws and regulations should not guide healthcare hiring practices in ASCs. HCEs need to become more familiar with the SOP of CRNAs and the role of CRNAs as independent anesthesia providers in the healthcare arena. Marketing strategies directed at correcting these misconceptions should be the focus of efforts from the AANA to decrease the gap in knowledge that HCEs have regarding CRNA SOP.

This author recommends two specific strategies, based on the results of this exploratory project. The first focus should be to inform HCEs of best evidence-based practices, which include the hiring of CRNAs at ASCs. This should be accomplished by the AANA representation and attendance at the California Ambulatory Surgical Association (CASA) annual meeting, which would include a poster presentation, as well as efforts to collaborate with the HCEs about concerns they may have regarding hiring CRNAs in ASCs. This may enhance professional relationships between CRNAs and HCEs in California, and therefore increase the hiring of CRNAs for ASCs. Although there is a financial cost to participate in this meeting, the benefits to CRNA advocacy would be significant both for CRNAs in California and other states. California has the

most significant number of ASCs in the nation that employ a large percentage of the nation's HCEs, who are chief administrators in ASCs (Ambulatory Surgery Center Association, n.d.). The booth would need to be reserved in advance and could be staffed by AANA members knowledgeable about legal and current CRNA SOP regulations. A professional poster would be featured in the booth to highlight current state and federal regulations. The CRNA anesthesia group, Sweet Dreams Anesthesia™, has reserved an Elite level booth at the September 2020 CASA meeting. If time allows, contacting this group and sharing the results and recommendations of this project could provide a speedy way for the AANA to inform the HCEs of the best evidence-based practices.

A second recommendation highlights the need for further research investigating patients' perceptions of the care they received from CRNAs. The surveys could be part of a post-operative patient questionnaire designed to understand the patients' experiences while receiving care at ASCs. Survey results would be shared with the HCEs at each of the ASCs, thereby informing HCEs of the quality of care provided by CRNAs. Also, information regarding CRNA practices would be included on the back of the patient survey. It would be geared toward educating the general public and highlighting the specific needs of the anesthesia patient. This survey could be distributed to HCEs at all ASCs in California. The AANA website could also provide a digital version, where CRNAs could print out and distribute the survey to their patients.

Patient Survey

Thank you for allowing me to care for you today. Please answer these questions based on the care I provided today as your CRNA anesthesia provider.

Please answer on a scale of 1-5: 1 being the least and five being the most.

1. Preoperatively, I was comfortable with my CRNAs professional manner and level of expertise. ____
2. I was adequately informed about the anesthesia care I was going to receive. ____
3. I felt supported by the CRNA during my anesthesia experience. ____
4. I would choose this CRNA again if I needed anesthesia services in the future. ____
5. Additional comments:

Back

Anesthesia Provider –Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNA)

Who is my Anesthesia provider?

- CRNAs are advanced nursing professionals who safely administer *more than 49 million anesthetics* to patients each year in the United States (American Association of Nurse Anesthetists, 2019)
- CRNAs practice in every setting in which anesthesia is delivered: traditional hospital surgical suites and obstetrical delivery rooms; critical access hospitals; ambulatory surgical centers; the offices of dentists, podiatrists, ophthalmologists, plastic surgeons, and pain management specialists; and U.S. military, Public Health Services, and Department of Veterans Affairs healthcare facilities.
- CRNA services include pre-anesthesia evaluation, administering the anesthetic, monitoring and interpreting the patient's vital signs and managing the patient throughout surgery, and post-operative pain control.

I was your anesthesia provider today for your procedure. Thank you for your trust. I wish you a speedy recovery and good health. For more information on CRNAs and the scope of practice regulations, please visit the American Association of Nurse Anesthetist website at www.aana.com.

SIGNATURE OF CRNA _____